

Oily effluents as source of water environment pollution

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Abstract

There are described the adverse effects on the water environment (WE) caused by the oily effluents (OE). In particular, those are the energy & heat exchange imbalance between layers of water masses, the albedo reduction of seawater, the death of many marine animals and the pathological changes in organs and tissues of living organisms. The stages are listed of the processes having place in the oil pollutants trapped in WE that lead to the water physical properties deterioration such as changes in color, taste and smell. It is shown that among the main sources of the OE formation, there are the oil refineries, the gas stations, the filling stations and the pumping stations of the main oil pipelines. The main physical and chemical properties of OE that affect the OE action in WE are as follows: density, viscosity, solidification temperature, evaporation potential, and toxicity. The existing methods of OE purification from impurities containing oil and oil products are given here as follows: mechanical, chemical, physical-chemical and biological methods. The brief description of each method is given. The possible ways and methods are shown of untreated OE entering prevention into administrative, technical, and technological WE.

Keywords: Oily effluents, Sources of formation, Physical-chemical properties, Toxic properties, Purification, Ways, Methods, Prevention, Contamination.

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1. Introduction

In the recent years, the pollution of the planet water basin has increased significantly. Every year, for whatever reason, from 2 to 10 million tons of oil and oil products are emitted into the World Ocean. The aerial survey from the satellites shows that almost 30% of the ocean surface is covered with the oil film. Along with it, it was found that one of the most common anthropogenic pollutants is OE.

It was shown [1] that the world ocean pollution with the oil products makes the extremely negative impact on WE. In particular, the following effects have place: the imbalance of the energy & heat exchange between layers of the water masses; the albedo decrease of the water; the death of many marine life species; the pathological changes in organs and tissues of living organisms.

Regarding oil pollutants (oil, oil products, oily non-solutes) getting into WE and affecting the water surface, the process of its subsequent aggravation is usually divided into the following stages the [1]:

- ❖ evaporation of light-boiling components;
- ❖ dissolution of some components; the absorption by hydrobionts with their subsequent transformation;
- ❖ bacterial oxidation at depth;
- ❖ sedimentation onto the bottom;
- ❖ accumulation in the ground and entering to the waters of the aquifer;
- ❖ emulsification;
- ❖ water-oil resinous balls formation polluting the coast;
- ❖ photo-oxidation of oil components in coastal waters;
- ❖ bacterial oxidation on the water surface.

In general, the WE oil pollution leads to deterioration of the water physical properties such as changes in color, taste, and smell. The oil pollution of waters takes various forms. Initially in the emission cases, the thickness of the oil coating may be several centimeters. While spreading, the cover forms a thin film on the surface of the water, which prevents the air oxygen penetration into the water. At the 4 mm film thickness and the 17 mg/l oil concentration in

the water, the amount of the dissolved oxygen decreases by 40% in 20 days. The oil concentration growth to 20-23 mg/l causes a dexterity impairment and death of fish. Over time, an oil-in-water or water-in-oil emulsion is formed. Later on, lumps of oil heavy fraction emerge; those oil aggregates can float on the WE surface for a long time.

The oil products in water affect the organoleptic characteristics of the water. The obtained results of the researches show that in the water contaminated with the oil products, soon, fish meat gets a taste of oil. This occurs in a day at a concentration of 0.5 mg/l of oil products, in 3 days at 0.2 mg/l and in 10 days at 0.1 mg/l.

All this makes it necessary to conduct special OE research aimed at reducing and preventing the ingress of the untreated oily non-solutes in WE as much as possible.

Figure 1. Neva pollution by oil. [2]

2. Development

This article is aimed at analysis of the sources of the OE formation and of their physical-chemical and toxic properties important for the WE contamination and the methods of the water purification. Also in the article, possible ways and methods are suggested for prevention of untreated OE penetration into WE.

Among the main sources of OE formation, there are refineries, gas stations, filling stations and pumping stations of the main oil pipelines. OE from these sources are divided into production-born, household and storm water sources. The oily effluents volume and composition depends on the following factors: the number and capacity of the tanks; the availability of pumping/boiling/filling facilities and discharge platforms, garages, mechanical workshops, etc. Also the oily effluents volume depends on the type of the oils and oil products, which are used for the relevant operations performing.

Figure 2. Neva pollution by oil. [2]

In addition, a large amount of OE is generated at refineries transferring the effluents to onshore treatment facilities: namely the effluents are ballasting, flushing and bilge waters from the vessels of the waterborne transport (WT). The ballast water is formed, when a WT tanker, while transporting oil and oil products, is forced to accept seawater as the water ballast. Being mixed with the remaining cargo in the tanks, the ballast water is contaminated with oil; and in such cases,

the oil content can reach about 5000-10000 mg/l. As for the bilge water, this is the wastewater formed in the engine rooms of WT vessels and containing oil and oil products accumulated under the bottom boards [3].

In the OE composition, oil can be contained in the form of large droplets ranging in size from hundreds millimeters or more or in the form of an emulsion with particle size of 40-50 nm. The large oil particles float up easily and form a film on the water surface, while the emulsified ones are suspended in the water, which dramatically complicates the process of their removal from the water. The amount of the emulsified oil products varies in the range of 12-36% of the total oil content in the oily waters.

The main physical and chemical properties of OE that determine their behavior in WE are as follows: density, viscosity, solidification temperature, evaporation potential, and toxicity [4].

The density of various oil products contained in the OE at 20°C varies in the following ranges (kg/m³): gasoline 700-780, diesel fuel 830-860, jet fuel 755-840, boiler fuel 870-900, engine oil 880-915 and heating oil 940-970.

The OE viscosity means the resistance to displacement of a liquid layer against another and characterizes the oil product fluidity. The larger it is, the lower the fluidity of the oil product.

The solidification temperature describes the temperature, at which an oil product loses its mobility. The highest temperature, at which the level of the oil product remains immobile for 1 minute, is taken as the solidification temperature. The value of the solidification temperature is directly proportional to the content of resins and paraffins in the oil product.

The evaporation potential characterizes the property of the oil products to pass from their liquid state to the gaseous state at a temperature lower than the boiling point. In this case, the evaporation of a hydrocarbon liquid occurs at any temperature until the gas space above it is completely saturated with the hydrocarbons.

Table 1. Recommendations for choosing a water purification method from oil products.

Concentration*	Optimal purification process	Additional conditions
More than 1000	Water settling in oil traps	Pop-up speed is more than 0.5 mm/s. At least 60% of oil products are trapped
	Centrifugal separation in a hydrocyclone	Pop-up speed is more than 0.3 mm/s. At least 60% of oil products are removed
300 - 1000	Water settling in oil traps with preliminary destabilization	Purification effect depends on the settling duration.
	Flotation with coagulation and pre-destabilization	Purification effect is up to 70%
20 - 300	Flotation with coagulation and pre-destabilization	Purification effect is up to 60%
	Electro-coagulation and flotation with pre-destabilization	Purification effect is up to 70%
Less than 20	Filtration through granular materials with coagulation and pre-destabilization	Concentration of oil products in purified water is less than 10 mg/l

*(mg/l). **Source:** Authors.

The toxicity of the oil products being part of OE shows itself in the fact that their vapors exert a toxic effect on the human body. Especially harmful are heavy gasoline kinds containing benzol and leaded gasoline (due to the presence of the tetraethyl lead). Dangerous to human health, the content of gasoline, naphtha and kerosene vapors in the air makes 0.3 mg/l. When humans are exposed to the petroleum vapors, the increased incidence of respiratory diseases, the functional changes in the nervous system & the blood pressure and a slowing down of the pulse are observed.

If the oil concentration in the seawater makes 0.1 to 0.01 ml/l, the fish eggs die within a few days. In the case of the oil film presence in the seawater, more than 100 million fish larvae can die on 1 ha of the sea surface.

Currently, there is a large number of extraction ways of the oil products from OE. However every one of them is effective only in a certain range of the oil products concentration, as shown in the Table (1) [5].

If the initial oil products concentration is less than 300 mg/l, it is possible not to use a sand trap or an oil trap but instead to clean the wastewaters only with aid of a pressure flotation unit and a sorption filter. Thus, in order to design treatment schemes,

it is necessary to know the source of the oily wastewaters formation and the initial concentration of the oil products. The main methods of OE cleaning from oil and oil products impurities are as follows: mechanical, chemical, physical-chemical and biological methods [6].

The essence and content of each of these methods can be described as follows.

3. Methods

3.1 Mechanical methods

As an independent method, the OE mechanical purification is used in the cases, when the water subjected to the procedure by this method is suitable either for use for the needs of the technological production processes, or can be poured down into the natural water basin without causing any harm to its environmental condition. In all other cases, this method is used only for the primary purification of water from the oil products impurities. The mechanical purification method makes it possible to remove from 60 to 65% of suspended particles of various substances. The most commonly used methods of the mechanical OE purification from oil and oil product contaminants are as follows:

sedimentation, centrifugal removal of water-polluting impurities, and filtration.

During settling, if the impurities have the density higher than that of the water, they settle to the bottom, and, on the contrary, if the impurities density is lower than that of water, they float up to the surface. The structures used for this method of the mechanical purification are called sludge traps. They are reservoirs, in which wastewaters are treated, while at rest.

3.2 Chemical methods

The essence of the chemical methods is the addition of specially developed chemical reagents to the treated wastewater that react with the oil pollution and the oil products. Often, these chemicals cause impurities falling out in the form of the precipitation. Most often, this takes place due to the oxidation of the hydrocarbon components of the oil and its derivatives. One of these methods of the wastewater chemical treatment from the oil pollution is the chemical ozonation.

3.3 Physical-chemical methods

The main methods of the physical-chemical wastewater treatment are coagulation, flotation and sorption.

The essence of the coagulation process is the accelerated transformation of fine-dispersed (when particle size is from 1 to 100 micrometers) and emulsified types of contaminants into larger formations, which then fall out as a precipitate. As a rule, this process is stimulated by special chemical reagents called coagulants. Their action leads to the formation (in water) of flakes having a weak electrostatic positive charge. Such flakes having the weak electrostatic charge begin interacting with oil impurities being in the colloidal state. Electro-statically, the coagulant attracts those impurities, which results in their fall out under the gravity action; so on the bottom of the treatment tank, they form some sediment distinguished with a loose structure. Then the impurities are easily removed from there.

On the contrary, the flotation process leads to a stable foam formation on the surface of the treated water. With aid of this foam, the harmful impurities of oil and its derivatives are captured and retained for a long time [7]. Also this foam layer is easily separated from the treated effluents. The basis of the above-described foam is the stable connection of air or gas bubbles with the oil

particles. This process (based on the principle of the flotation bubbles formation) is divided into three types: mechanical flotation, vacuum flotation and electro-flotation.

The mechanical flotation involves the foaming caused by the fragmentation of water drops by the air flow created by means of special turbines called jets. In this process, also either an injector or a porous plate is used.

The principle of the vacuum flotation consists in creating of a vacuum zone inside of the chamber of the vacuum flotation device. In these rarified conditions, any air dissolved in the water is released in the form of the bubbles.

The electro-flotation used for the foam creation requires passing a constant electric current through the treated water with the oil pollutants in its content. This process results in the saturation of water with gaseous hydrogen bubbles formed at the cathode. However, the highest degree of the oil effluents purification is achieved only with use of the sorption method.

3.4 Biological methods

Currently, the biological treatment methods are considered to be the most promising direction in this area. The essence of these methods consists in the use of the ability of various microorganisms to break down and assimilate harmful impurities, which results in the water purification from the oil and its derivatives. In other words, the crude oil and the oil products are used by the microorganisms in their life activities as food sources. With the use of the biological purification methods, the oxidation of the oil impurities transforms them in absolutely safe products: carbon dioxide, ordinary water, nitrate and sulfate salts, and other harmless compounds.

The use of the biological methods for the effluents purification from the impurities in the form of oil and its derivatives involves the use of special aeration tanks and biological filters. As a rule, the biological filters are the large reinforced concrete tanks equipped with perforated bottoms. Inside of these tanks, there is a granular filtration material such as crushed stone, slag or granular plastic. This filtering material is subjected to irrigation with a special medium containing microorganisms. The process itself of the oily effluents purification is done due to the vital activity of these microorganisms that dwell on the

filter surface and form the so-called biological film on it.

The presented here analysis of the available research results in relation to OE treatment allows us to highlight the following possible ways and methods of the untreated OE ingress preventing into WE:

- ❖ *Administrative methods*: introduction of stricter requirements, sanctions and penalties for an unauthorized OE discharge into WE; implementation of measures aimed at rapid and high-quality overcoming of emergency situations with OE spills; improvement of the treatment organization of OE generated at production and transport facilities; implementation of measures aimed at possible accidents preventing on WT vessels and tankers;
- ❖ *Technical methods*: making environmentally friendly the technical means and equipment causing the OE formation; development of new and improvement of existing technical means (stations) for OE collecting and cleaning;
- ❖ *Technological methods*: making environmentally friendly technological processes leading to the OE formation; development of new and improvement of existing OE cleaning methods.

4. Conclusions and suggestions

- I. One of the most common anthropogenic pollutants of the World's Ocean is OE; the oily effluents affect the organoleptic characteristics of water significantly. In the water contaminated with the oil products, fish meat gets the taste of oil after a day at the oil products concentration 0.5 mg/l of, in 3 days at 0.2 mg/l and after 10 days at 0.1 mg/l.
- II. Among the main sources of the OE formation are refineries, gas stations, filling stations and pumping stations of the main oil pipelines.
- III. The main physical and chemical properties of OE that determine the oil pollution behavior in WE are as follows:

density, viscosity, solidification temperature, evaporation potential, and toxicity. The toxicity of oil products being part of OE consists in the fact that their vapors have a toxic effect on the human body. When humans are exposed to the petroleum vapors, the incidence grows of respiratory diseases, functional changes in the nervous system and blood pressure, and slowing down of the pulse.

- IV. The main methods of OE purification from the oil and oil products impurities are as follows: mechanical methods; chemical methods; physical and chemical methods; biological methods.
- V. The possible ways and methods of preventing WE contamination with OE are the implementation of a set of specific administrative, technical and technological measures.

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